

PSEUDOSCIENTIFIC BELIEFS, MEDIA LITERACY, AND NEED FOR TEACHER EDUCATION

Deepali Gupta¹ & Ajay Kumar Singh²

¹*Ph.D. Research Scholar, School of Education, Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU), New Delhi, India*

²*Professor, School of Education, Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU), New Delhi, India*

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Abstract

In the present information-rich world, media resources are increasingly responsible for promoting pseudoscientific beliefs, because the misinformation is proliferating readily due to the use of these resources. These media resources disseminate myths and unscientific knowledge in the absence of the ability to differentiate between unscientific knowledge, specifically in the academic space where teachers and students are directly influenced by media resources. It is essential for teachers to critically examine the media content and differentiate between scientifically valid information and misconceptions. Media literacy is the only way to combat these issues in educational practices. A previous study revealed a lower ability among teachers to discern fact from fiction. They emphasised the role of media literacy in addressing pseudoscientific beliefs among teachers. Therefore, a correlational survey was employed using a five-point Likert scale to determine the level and relationship between media literacy and pseudoscientific beliefs among school teachers in Indian schools.

Keywords: *Media Literacy, Pseudoscientific Beliefs, School Teachers, Teacher Training, and Teacher Education*

I. INTRODUCTION

There is a rapid proliferation of digital media resources and democratized access to information, which has simultaneously amplified the dissemination of misinformation and pseudoscientific claims. Teachers play an important role in nurturing the students' scientific understanding and providing them with valid information. However, their susceptibility to pseudoscientific beliefs can undermine teachers' roles towards their students. In this scenario, media literacy can critically analyse media resources and their content, and it is increasingly recognised as a key skill in addressing the misinformation (Potter, 2018) in academics and in general. So, this study examines the prevalence of pseudoscientific beliefs and media literacy level and their existing relationship between both pseudoscientific beliefs and media literacy among school teachers.

Pseudoscience is the theories and arguments that are not supported by empirical data and contradict scientific principles, yet utilise scientific jargon to appear legitimate (Kızılcık, 2024). Pseudoscience refers to those practices that are presented as scientific but lack empirical support or adherence to the scientific method (Shermer, 2002). Globally, beliefs from astrology to vaccine misinformation are prevalent and often rooted in biases in cultural, social, and cognitive origin areas (Lobato et al., 2014). In India, due to a diverse cultural background, such beliefs may be rooted in tradition and societal norms. There is a greater chance of spreading among students through their teachers in the absence of the ability to differentiate between scientific knowledge. If teachers themselves possess these beliefs, it can restrict them from promoting scientific knowledge in their students.

E.V. Ramasamy, Jyotiba Phule, and Periyar challenged superstitions and unscientific practices to promote a rational and scientific outlook among people and the future generation. Even in present-day Kerala, Sasthra Sahithya Parishad and other organisations continue working in this area to encourage scientific practices for social revolution. These organisations are also active in the scientific literacy movement, environmental awareness, and health campaigns. The rationalists and activists Narendra Dabholkar, Govind Pansare, M.M. Kalburgi, and Gauri Lankesh highlight the risks, struggles, and deep roots in India. The huge barriers were faced by anti-superstition activists in the past, although there continued debates on astrology, Vastu Shastra, untested alternative medicine, and miracle claims.

Media literacy is the ability to analyze, access, evaluate, and transmit messages in various written and unwritten formats (İnceoğlu, 2007). This multifaceted capability equips people to receive media information, interpret it critically, and express their thoughts and beliefs (Shibata, 2003). To access, analyse, evaluate, and create media content, media literacy contains the needed skills (Livingstone, 2004). Media literacy is an analytical and critical tool in identifying misinformation and developing informed decision-making. Enhanced media literacy has been linked to reduced susceptibility to pseudoscientific claims (Lewandowsky et al., 2012). Students' knowledge is always affected by teachers' understanding and their pedagogical practices. Studies indicate that gaps in teachers' critical thinking skills can perpetuate the spread of pseudoscientific beliefs in classrooms (Allchin, 2011). A media-literate teacher can better understand media outputs and their impact on individuals (Kızılcık, 2024).

So, this study argues that pseudoscientific beliefs are promoted by media resources and disseminate unscientific knowledge among academics. Therefore, the teachers must be able to differentiate between pseudoscience and legitimate knowledge. Teachers may transfer this knowledge to their students, who may reflect on this inclination if they adapt the content without ensuring its scientific validity. Thus, critical competencies and capabilities such as inference, problem-solving, explanation, analysis, synthesis, interpretation, open-mindedness, and self-regulation can differentiate science from pseudoscience (Castelão & Lawless, 2002). Therefore, it becomes vital to understand how teachers comprehend, respond to, and evaluate media to reduce the dissemination of non-scientific knowledge and to enhance scientific thinking among their students.

II. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study aims to address the following questions:

1. What is the level of media literacy and pseudoscientific beliefs among school teachers?
2. Is there any correlation between media literacy and pseudoscientific beliefs and their factors among school teachers?

III. METHODOLOGY

In the present research, a survey correlational research design was utilised among teachers who had not previously engaged in any form of media literacy training. The data collection process was conducted online via a questionnaire disseminated through Google Forms. Both the Media Literacy Scale (MLS) and the Pseudoscientific Belief Scale (PBS) were constructed and published in the Turkish language and are accessible in the public domain. The Media Literacy Scale (MLS) was disseminated within the framework of a doctoral dissertation, whereas the Pseudoscientific Belief Scale (PBS) was published in a scholarly article in Turkey. In alignment with the objectives of this inquiry, aimed at understanding the extent to which educators interacted with media-generated information, the Pseudoscientific Belief Scale (PBS), translated into English by Kızılcık (2024) and initially developed by Çetinkaya and Taşar (2018), was employed. This particular scale was chosen due to its inclusion of a spectrum of beliefs ranging from unverified physical phenomena to dubious health interventions. The Pseudoscientific Belief Scale consists of 21 items formatted in a five-point Likert scale and is categorized into three distinct factors: Pseudo-physical claims, pseudo-predictive claims, and Pseudo-medical claims

S1-F1: Pseudo-physical claims are non-scientific explanations of events that are physical in nature and misuse scientific terms, for example, energy fields, telekinesis, or mystical powers.

S1-F2: Pseudo-predictive claims are beliefs to predict the future, such as astrology, fortune-telling, and numerology, without valid evidence.

S1-F2: Pseudo-medical claims are unverified health practices that lack scientific processes, such as anti-vaccine views and miracle cures.

In parallel, to know the teachers' engagement with media resources, the Media Literacy Scale was employed. It is translated by the researcher into English and Hindi for this study. Tüzcel (2012) originally developed the Media Literacy Scale, which comprises 30 items in a five-point Likert scale. These 30 items are grouped into the three factors: confidence, literacy, and dependency.

S2-F1: Confidence reflects the individual's trust in media resources and their production of content without verification.

S2-F2: Literacy denotes the individual capacity to comprehend, analyse, and evaluate the media resources and their content.

S2-F3: Dependency signifies the extent to which individuals are media dependent for various information, entertainment, or social connections.

The two scales were employed as they comprehensively address the factors related to pseudoscience and media literacy, thereby aligning with the objectives of this study. Data were collected from a sample of 50 school teachers representing both government and private institutions in the states of Uttar Pradesh and Uttarakhand. In addition, a few teachers from Delhi and neighbouring states also participated in the study. The participants represented

diverse subject streams and had teaching experience ranging from one to twenty years across primary, middle, and secondary levels. Their ages ranged from 20 to 50 years. The teachers were selected based on the researcher’s prior professional interactions with them during their period of service.

The purpose of this study was to determine the level and relationship between pseudoscientific beliefs and media literacy among school teachers. So, to fulfil this objective, firstly, the level of pseudoscientific belief and media literacy was examined; after that, the correlation between pseudoscientific belief and media literacy was determined. The obtained data was analysed using spreadsheets and MS Excel software. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to determine the level of pseudoscientific belief and media literacy. Spearman correlations were used to examine the relationship between pseudoscientific belief and media literacy. This statistic used by researchers in this study is appropriate for analysing the obtained data because the sample has a normal distribution due to the use of the non-random sampling method to fulfil the objective.

In the obtained responses, the number 5 shows a high scientific value or media literacy level, while the number 1 shows a low scientific value and media literacy level for the positive meaning items. The criteria were inverted for the coding of negative meaning items for both pseudoscientific belief and media literacy scales. The analysis criteria were determined according to the structure of the scale, which is a five-point Likert scale. So, the respondent responded 1-5 on each item of the scale. The criteria for analysis are given in Table 1.

TABLE I. ANALYSIS CRITERIA

Level of Ranges	Level
1.00-1.79	Very low (VL)
1.80-2.59	low (L)
2.60-3.39	Moderate (M)
3.40-4.19	High (M)
4.20-5.00	Very High (VH)

IV. FINDINGS

The findings were obtained after analysing the data present in tables II, III, and IV. Table I shows the descriptive statistics of the pseudo-scientific scale, Table III shows the descriptive statistics of the media literacy scale, while Table IV shows the correlation between the pseudo-scientific scale and the media literacy scale and the factors of both the pseudo-scientific scale and the media literacy scale.

In Table II, the descriptive statistics of the pseudo-scientific scale show the key pattern in all three factors in pseudoscience belief, which are pseudo-physical claims (S1-F1), pseudo-predictive claims (S1-F2), and pseudo-medical claims (S1-F3). There are consistent moderate levels across three factors, with the mean distribution spread over varied responses among school teachers. These results represent a susceptibility to pseudoscientific knowledge among school teachers that does not significantly vary in the three factors of the claim: pseudo-physical claims, pseudo-predictive claims, and pseudo-medical claims of the pseudoscientific scale due to this consistent medium level. This inconsistent level implies a more generalised

approach to how teachers process and respond to the information, rather than specific vulnerabilities tied to particular types of pseudoscientific content.

Factor	Mean	Level	Standard Deviation
S1-F1: Pseudo-physical claims	2.9344	Moderate	.42802
S1-F2: Pseudo-predictive claim	3.0833	Moderate	.50973
S1-F3: Pseudo-medical claims	2.9300	Medium	.71479

TABLE II. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF THE PSEUDOSCIENTIFIC SCALE.

At the same time, Table III, the descriptive statistics media literacy scale, shows the key pattern in all three factors in media literacy, that is, confidence (S2-F1), literacy (S2-F2), and dependency (S2-F3). There are moderate levels for both confidence and literacy, yet a high level for the third factor, media dependency, with the mean distribution spread over varied responses. These results represent significant variation in the three factors of confidence, literacy, and dependency of the media literacy scale among school teachers. This result shows that the school teachers have a moderate level of confidence and literacy while using media resources, but they are highly dependent on the media resource for getting the information.

Factor	Mean	Level	Standard Deviation
S2-F1: Confidence	3.2245	Moderate	.31037
S2-F2: Literacy	3.0357	Moderate	.59908
S2-F3: Dependency	3.4275	Higher	.22467

TABLE III. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF THE MEDIA SCALE.

The correlation between the factors of both the pseudo-scientific scale and the media literacy scale is present in Table 5. The correlation coefficient between S1-F2 (pseudo-predictive claim) and S1-F3 (pseudo-medical claims) is 0.659, denoting a strongly positive correlation. It indicates that teachers who have pseudo-predictive beliefs also support pseudo-medical claims. The correlations between S1-F1 (pseudo-physical claims) and S1-F2 (pseudo-predictive claims) are 0.718, denoting a strongly positive relationship, while the correlation between S1-F1 (pseudo-physical claims) and S1-F3 (pseudo-medical claims) is 0.660, which also denotes a strongly positive relationship. These results overall suggest a strong positive relationship exists among pseudoscience factors; as one factor increases, the others tend to increase as well. Table V presents a correlation between pseudo-scientific factors and a correlation among media literacy factors. The correlation coefficient between S2-F2 (Literacy) and S2-F3 (Dependency) is -0.265, indicating a weak negative correlation. This suggests that individuals possessing higher media literacy often exhibit decreased reliance on media. The correlations of S2-F1 (Confidence) with S2-F2 and S2-F3 are -0.149 and 0.283, respectively, suggesting a weak negative and moderate positive relationship. This indicates that an individual's confidence in

the media is increased, and the media dependency decreases, while dependency, on the other hand, increases to some extent with their media literacy.

The correlation coefficient between S1-F1 (pseudo-physical claims) and S2-F1 (confidence) is 0.12, indicating a very weak positive relationship. This result indicates that individuals with greater confidence in the media to some extent support pseudo-physical claims. The correlation between S1-F3 (pseudo-medical claims) and S2-F2 (literacy) is 0.01, indicating a very weak positive relationship. This suggests that individuals possessing higher media literacy are likely to endorse pseudo-medical claims.

TABLE V. SPEARMAN CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS OF FACTORS

		S1F1	S1F2	S1F3	S2F1	S2F2
S1F2	Correlation Coefficient	.718**				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0				
S1F3	Correlation Coefficient	.660**	.659**			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0			
S2F1	Correlation Coefficient	0.12	0.173	0.25		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.401	0.223	0.076		
S2F2	Correlation Coefficient	0	-0.149	0.01	0.099	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.997	0.298	0.946	0.491	
S2F3	Correlation Coefficient	0.023	-0.106	-0.077	.283*	-0.265
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.871	0.459	0.591	0.044	0.06

V. DISCUSSION

The findings of this study revealed that teachers exhibited a moderate level of pseudoscientific beliefs across the three factors: pseudo-physical, pseudo-predictive, and pseudo-medical claims, establishing a baseline susceptibility. On the other hand, teachers have a high dependency on media for information, alongside moderate media literacy and confidence. This suggests a disproportionate distribution of media literacy factors among educators. The levels of both constructs show that while teachers are often exposed to media content, due to their moderate level of media literacy and high exposure, they do not necessarily correlate with strong critical skills, resulting in uncritical acceptance. This result shows that media platforms could serve as an extensive source for the generalisation of pseudoscientific beliefs. It also creates an environment for the widespread dissemination of misinformation and pseudoscientific narratives, which highlights a significant challenge for education.

Opposite to this result, Kızılcık (2024) found that pre-service teachers have a high level of media literacy and pseudo-scientific beliefs. Lobato et al. (2014) found in their study that moderate to strong positive correlations existed between the three categories—paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific claims—among the university population. Castela-Lawless (2002) also revealed the inability to demarcate science from pseudoscience in high school students, even when they are knowledgeable of scientific principles. Livingstone's (2004) article raised some critical issues for new media literacy in any policy of promoting media literacy among the university population. Some studies on the ability to demarcate pseudoscience from science demonstrated that people face difficulty in differentiating between these two (Çetinkaya et al., 2015; Turgut, 2009). In some studies, the teachers and pupil

teachers belong to different subjects and levels and are not sure about the science and pseudoscience concept (Gül, 2016; Gürgil, 2019). So, before entering their careers, teachers need to have the necessary knowledge and skills to differentiate between science and pseudoscience (Kızılcık, 2024). However, this study result shows that school teachers have consistently moderate pseudoscience belief levels, while the media literacy factor, confidence, literacy, and dependency are moderate to high levels.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this study, a moderate level of pseudoscientific beliefs across the three identified factors of pseudoscience suggests that pseudoscientific ideas do not significantly influence many teachers; these beliefs persist to a notable extent within the teaching community. Such a level of susceptibility may have implications for classroom teaching, particularly in developing a scientific temper among their students. This issue requires a systematic effort to understand those factors contributing to these beliefs and implement strategies to replace and challenge them with evidence-based comprehension.

An analysis of the Media Literacy Scale revealed variability in teachers' media literacy skills. (moderate proficiency in two factors and high proficiency) show that some aspects of media literacy are well-developed. However, some areas demand improvement, which reflects the importance of media literacy training programmes focusing on weaker areas while reinforcing existing strengths. These interventions have the strength to help teachers navigate the complex media landscape in India and equip them with the tools to evaluate and interpret information critically.

Integrating media literacy training into teacher education programs is an important step toward building the capability of teachers to assess information and resist pseudoscientific claims critically. Livingstone S. (2004) suggested extending the awareness of media literacy to include the culturally and historically orientated relationship between the symbolic and physical manifestation of knowledge, culture, and values. Therefore, the educational policies should prioritize media literacy as a core competency for teachers and embed it into pre-service and in-service training programs. This approach ensures that educators are well-prepared to navigate and counter misinformation in an increasingly digital and media-saturated environment. Regular workshops, updated resources, and hands-on activities should be integral components of such programmes to enhance teachers' media literacy skills continuously.

Moreover, integrating these competencies into curriculum frameworks would encourage teachers to transfer these skills to their students, thereby creating a ripple effect of informed and critical media consumers. Castelhão-Lawless (2002) focused on the teacher-educator role to change people's minds by providing them with proper methodologies that help them to find a difference between scientifically sound and unsound knowledge. Only then can we say that we have a scientifically literate population, capable of making serious science policy decisions. Future studies could broaden the scope by increasing the size of the sample to include participants from diverse educational contexts, such as rural, urban, and semi-urban settings, and examining the long-term impacts of media literacy training on teaching practices. Apart from this, research could explore the intersection of media literacy with other essential teacher competencies, such as fostering inclusivity and promoting scientific temper, to develop

comprehensive strategies for holistic teacher education. It underscores the need to focus on specific media literacy competencies, such as recognising logical fallacies, evaluating the credibility of sources, and identifying biases. By fostering these skills, teachers can become more resilient to misinformation and better equipped to educate their students about critical thinking and evidence-based reasoning.

In India, the movement against pseudoscience has deep roots in social reform, gained momentum with People's Science Movements, and continues through rationalist organisations, legal battles, and science communication efforts. It is both a grassroots social struggle and a constitutional and institutional duty tied to India's vision of a modern, democratic, scientific society. The awareness regarding pseudoscience in both teachers and students can lead to a better, rational, scientific, and growing society. In this direction, the media can play the role of a game changer if they deliver valid and scientific content and knowledge. The people with scientific knowledge can lead not only locally but also globally in a competitive international world.

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